

MAJOR ROLE OF MICRO, SMALL AND MEDIUM ENTERPRISES (MSMES) SECTOR IN NORTH EAST INDIA

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Abstract:

The Micro, Small, and Medium Enterprises (MSME) sector has grown to be a vibrant area of the Indian economy and a crucial engine of the economic cycle. It generates the second highest employment possibilities and significantly aids in the growth of entrepreneurship. The MSME sector significantly contributes to the growth of the Indian economy, accounting for more than sixty-three million three hundred eighty thousand enterprises, over forty percent of exports, over twenty-eight percent of the GDP, and providing employment for about one hundred eleven million people. In this paper, an attempt has been made to analyse the major role of the MSME sector in North East India, and a brief discussion of the current situation, employment status, an overview of the targeted activities, and the growth and distribution of MSME in North East India. To achieve the study's various objectives, various methodologies were used. Secondary data has been analyzed to investigate the significant role of the MSMEs sector in North East India. According to the findings and analyses, the MSMEs sector as a whole is the engine of growth for the Indian economy and North Eastern states development. According to the study, there is an increasing pattern in the number of units, employment, and asset market value. It is worth noting that there is a strong relationship between the total factory unit and employment. The role of the MSMEs sector is rapidly expanding, and it has become a focal point for future growth in rural and urban development, with significant policy implications.

Key Words: MSME, Entrepreneurship, Employment, Economic Development, North East India

Introduction:

Micro, Small, and Medium-Sized Enterprises (MSME) have grown to be a large and active segment of the Indian economy. MSMEs contribute significantly to the industrialization of rural and underdeveloped areas, which helps to even out regional differences and ensures a more equitable distribution of wealth. Additionally, they considerably contribute to the establishment of viable work opportunities at prices that are comparably less capital-intensive than those of large corporations. MSMEs considerably improve the socioeconomic level of the nation while serving as support units for large corporations. To address concerns about MSMEs-related policies, the Micro, Small, and Medium Enterprises Development (MSMED) Act was notified of the global coverage and investment cap in 2006. The Act aims to improve the operational capabilities and competitiveness of those businesses. The term "enterprise," which includes both manufacturing and repair enterprises, has now been recognised in a statutory framework. It makes an effort to combine the three business sizes-micro, small, and medium-and for the first time, defines medium corporations. The Act also establishes a process for legislative consultation with substantial national advisory requirements and fair representation of all relevant stakeholder groups, including the three different types of enterprises.

Generating income earmarked for marketing, corporate expansion, and heightened competitiveness It has been suggested that supporting small and microbusinesses will increase public understanding of the progressive credit policies. The manufacture of commodities, the generation of jobs, the promotion of entrepreneurship, export, wealth distribution, and India's economic development are all significantly influenced by Micro, Small, and Medium-Sized Enterprises (MSMEs). The industry currently employs over 11 million people and over 6 crore units. More than 49% of India's exports are MSMEs, which also contribute 30% of the country's GDP. MSMEs employ about 110.99 million people, which is second only to agriculture in terms of employment. 110.99 million of the population, or 49.78 million, lives in rural areas, while 61.21 million do so in urban areas. However, 36.23 million people work in various service sectors, 38.72 million in business, and 36.04 million in manufacturing. There are 84.47 million men and 26.49 million women employed in the United States. India's large population and lack of capital formation cause it to choose labor-intensive MSME industries to capital-intensive major businesses.

Review of Literature:

Dey (2014) in the study entitled "MSME in India: Its Growth and Prospects" analyzed the significance of MSMEs in both developed and developing countries in recent years. Additionally, the MSME sector can

contribute to understanding the goal of the future National Manufacturing Policy, which is to increase the manufacturing sector's GDP contribution from 16 percent to 25 percent by the end of 2022. The performance of MSMEs in India as of right now was the main topic of this essay. This study also found that MSMEs support the nation's exports, employment, and manufacturing production. (Dey, 2014)

Kumar et al., (2009) in the study titled “Micro, Small and Medium Enterprises (MSMEs) in India: challenges and issues in the current Scenario” focused on the fact that MSMEs play a significant role in the development of any economy. MSMEs account for 90% of industrial units and 40% of value creation in the manufacturing sector in India. The MSME sector currently plays a key role in output, exports, and employment. This sector accounts for 50% of all manufactured exports and 40% of gross industrial value added. A total of 13.2 million units are employed in the economy, manufacturing 6000 different commodities that range from simple to extremely complex goods. Approximately 32 million people are employed in this industry, which is the second largest employer after agriculture. The expansion and development of the MSME sector since the 1990s are also discussed in this article. The issues faced by MSMEs, as well as its marketing and the licence raj issue, are also discussed in this article. (Kumar, 2009)

Sahapathi and Khana (2011) in the paper “A brief study of the SWOT, Government role and Contribution in the development of the MSME’s of the Haryana region” described that the MSME sector of Haryana is fully competitive with the large scale industries. Any industry must have a strong infrastructure in place before it can benefit from it. Industries are supported by infrastructure. The government of Haryana has increased the sector's support infrastructure. Only when the current infrastructure permits it can the industry expand. This study finds that Haryana's infrastructure has improved. This essay focuses on the several elements required for the growth of this industry in Haryana. The government's participation, contribution, and the prospects for this industry in the state of Haryana are highlighted in this essay. (Sahapathi, 2011)

Sajeevan (2012) in his paper as “Present Status of MSME Statistics” an attempt has been made to look into the statistical database in Micro, Small and Medium Enterprises. The international standard for defining MSMEs was covered in the first segment, which also covered conceptual difficulties regarding the MSME sector. The document attempts to explain the various definitions used in various MSME sector data sets as well as the method for gathering data for the sector's periodic census. The most recent statistics on the MSME sector from the fourth all-India census are included in the paper's conclusion. (Sajeevan, 2012)

Objectives:

- To study the present scenario of MSME sector of North East India
- To study the status of employment through MSME sector of North East India
- To study the overview of the targeted activities for the MSME sector in North East India
- To analyze the distribution and growth of MSMEs among the North East India

Methodology of the Study:

This research has a descriptive focus. The study's foundation is made up of secondary data sources. Several journals, books, and periodicals, among other sources, have been used to acquire secondary data. Investigated the following reports as well: From 2011–2012 through 2021–2022, MSME's Annual Reports are accessible. The NSS 73rd Round Report has been consulted. The RBI Reports are also accessible. The researcher used secondary data for the analysis and conclusion.

Present Scenario of MSME Sector of North East India:

The North East Region (NER), which makes up barely 1.5% of MSMEs in India, is a vibrant melting pot of cultures, diverse tribes, and a wide variety of unique crafts. It has great potential to develop as the nation's center for Micro, Small, and Medium Enterprises. The NER includes the following states: Assam, Arunachal Pradesh, Manipur, Meghalaya, Mizoram, Nagaland, Sikkim, and Tripura.

Table 1: State-wise Distribution of Estimated Number of MSMEs

S.No	State	Estimated number of Enterprises (Number in lakh)			
		All			
		Micro	Small	Medium	MSME
1	Arunachal Pradesh	0.22	0.00	0.00	0.22
2	Assam	12.10	0.04	0.00	12.14
3	Manipur	1.80	0.00	0.00	1.80
4	Meghalaya	1.12	0.00	0.00	1.12
5	Mizoram	0.35	0.00	0.00	0.35
6	Nagaland	0.91	0.00	0.00	0.91
7	Sikkim	0.26	0.00	0.00	0.26
8	Tripura	2.10	0.01	0.00	2.11
	All	18.86	0.05	0.00	18.91

Source: Annual Report 2021-22 (MSME, Annual Report, 2021-2022)

Table 1 depicts the estimated number of MSME in North East India by state. During the fiscal year 2021-22, the total number of MSMEs distributed in the north-eastern states is Micro 18.86, Small 0.05, and Overall 18.91, which includes micro, small, and medium businesses.

Employment Status through MSMES in All of North East India's States:

The MSME sector is widely regarded as a driving force behind economic growth and the promotion of equitable development. The sector also benefits the economy by encouraging the development of industries in all regions of the country. The sector's main advantage is its employment potential at a low capital cost. (RBI, 2019) Employment is a critical issue that the MSME sector must address. Table 2 depicts the sectoral distribution of male and female workers.

Table 2: State-wise Distribution of Employees (2015-16)

S.No	State	Employment		
		Female	Male	Total
1	Arunachal Pradesh	0.11	0.29	0.40
2	Assam	1.78	16.37	18.15
3	Manipur	1.40	1.52	2.92
4	Meghalaya	0.72	1.19	1.91
5	Mizoram	0.28	0.34	0.62
6	Nagaland	0.59	1.18	1.77
7	Sikkim	0.14	0.31	0.45
8	Tripura	0.44	2.51	2.95
	All	5.46	23.71	29.17

Source: Annual Report 2021-22 (MSME, Annual Report, 2021-2022) (MSME, NSS 73rd Round Report , 2015-2016)

A total of 29.17 employees were distributed among the northeastern states in the employment section, with 23.71 males and 5.45 females.

Activities in the MSME Sector for the North-Eastern Region:

A budget of Rs. 1608.61 crore in BE 2021–22 had been aside specifically for the Region, which includes the States of Assam, Arunachal Pradesh, Manipur, Meghalaya, Mizoram, Nagaland, Sikkim, and Tripura, in accordance with the government's policy of allocating 10% of all funding for NER.

KVIC in the North-East:

To ensure the effective implementation and oversight of Khadi and Village Industries (KVI) programmes in the North Eastern Region, the Khadi and Village Industries Commission (KVIC) has a Zonal Office in Guwahati and other fields Offices across the NE States (NER). KVI programmes are being implemented in the region through State KVI Boards, recognised institutions, cooperative groups, and business owners. Some of the village businesses emerging in these hilly, impoverished regions include fruit and vegetable processing, beekeeping, the processing of cereals and pulses, pottery, fibre, soap, cane and bamboo, carpentry & blacksmithy, as well as Khadi & Polyvastra enterprises.

Table 3: State-wise Physical Performance of KVIC in NER during 2021-22

S.No	State	Upto 31.12.2021			Expected Upto 31.03.2022		
		Production (Rs. In Lakhs)	Sales (Rs. In Lakhs)	Cumulative Employment (Number)	Production (Rs. In Lakhs)	Sales (Rs. In Lakhs)	Cumulative Employment (Number)
1	Arunachal Pradesh	1.49	3.40	31	1.55	3.63	31
2	Assam	512.33	446.96	5144	538.25	478.69	5144
3	Manipur	5.88	3.55	179	6.12	3.80	179
4	Meghalaya	9.65	5.94	59	9.84	6.23	59
5	Mizoram	0.00	0.00	0	0.00	0.00	0
6	Nagaland	10.96	40.44	295	11.40	43.31	295
7	Sikkim	0.00	0.00	0	0.00	0.00	0
8	Tripura	0.00	0.00	0	0.00	0.00	0
	Total	540.31	500.29	5708	567.16	535.66	5708

Source: Annual Report 2021-22 (MSME, Annual Report, 2021-2022)

KVIC's physical performance in NER in 2021-22 has been divided into two sections. Up to December 31, 2021, with an expected extension to January 31, 2022. Assam had the highest performance in Production, Sales, and even Employment in both sections (up to 31-12-2021 and 31-3-22). Mizoram, Sikkim, and Tripura did not have any performances.

Table 4: Physical Performance by State of Village Industries in NER in 2021–2022

S.No	State	Upto 31.12.2021			Expected Upto 31.03.2022		
		Production (Rs. In Lakhs)	Sales (Rs. In Lakhs)	Cumulative Employment (Number)	Production (Rs. In Lakhs)	Sales (Rs. In Lakhs)	Cumulative Employment (Number)
1	Arunachal Pradesh	10210.09	15766.04	0.24	14610.77	22571.97	0.24
2	Assam	124681.26	184481.15	6.08	218392.63	327056.74	6.43
3	Manipur	53000.86	76693.30	1.40	91736.91	135014.98	1.57
4	Meghalaya	24059.41	34103.67	0.69	47439.68	69353.30	0.78
5	Mizoram	41911.41	66250.04	1.43	66660.91	105092.14	1.50
6	Nagaland	56047.92	77761.09	1.16	86790.55	122431.77	1.25
7	Sikkim	6502.54	9723.95	0.28	9419.03	14129.74	0.28
8	Tripura	41153.33	60796.33	1.36	64043.37	95322.38	1.43
	Total	357566.82	525575.57	12.64	599093.85	890973.02	13.48

Source: Annual Report 2021-22 (MSME, Annual Report, 2021-2022)

When compared to KVIC, the physical performance of states of Village industries was very high. Production had a total of 357566.82 up to 31-12-2021 and 599093.83 up to 31-03-2022. (Rs in lakhs). In sales from December 31, 2021 to March 31, 2022, a total of 525575.57 and 890973.02 were made. Commutative employment was 12.64 as of December 31, 2021, and 13.48 as of March 31, 2022.

Table 5: PMEGP-KVIC has made special efforts to offer employment in NER under PMEGP

S.No	State	Margin Money allocation (Rs. In Lakhs)	Margin Money utilized (Rs. In Lakhs)	Units assisted (Number)	Estimated Employment generated (Number)
1	Arunachal Pradesh	479.08	232.63	98	784
2	Assam	14589.04	4948.48	2939	23512
3	Manipur	5156.79	5899.03	1556	12448
4	Meghalaya	3837.48	579.65	359	2872
5	Mizoram	2893.48	1412.46	810	6480
6	Nagaland	4296.52	2045.47	740	5920
7	Sikkim	191.63	152.28	57	456
8	Tripura	3072.38	1829.57	842	6736
	Total	34516.4	17099.57	7401	59208

Source: Annual Report 2021-22 (MSME, Annual Report, 2021-2022)

A total number of 7,401 PMEGP Projects were assisted by utilizing Margin Money Subsidy of Rs 170.99 Crore in NE States during the year 2020-21. PMEGP performance in NE States during 2020-21. PMEGP-KVIC has made special efforts to provide PMEGP employment in NER. A total of 34516.4 was allotted, with 17099.57 used to assist 7401 units in various North Eastern states, with an estimated employment of 59208.

Table 6: PMEGP performance in NE States during 2021-22 (31.12.2021) is as under

S.No	State	Margin Money allocation (Rs. In Lakhs)	Margin Money utilized (Rs. In Lakhs)	Units assisted (Number)	Estimated Employment generated (Number)
1	Arunachal Pradesh	675.7	336.62	86	688
2	Assam	14887.25	2262.59	1282	10256
3	Manipur	6928.56	1599.65	460	3680
4	Meghalaya	3928.23	323.94	206	1648
5	Mizoram	2984.23	398.05	189	1512
6	Nagaland	4453.49	1281.32	490	3920
7	Sikkim	240.52	52.53	24	192
8	Tripura	3499.3	1058.65	453	3624
	Total	37597.28	7313.25	3190	25520

Source: Annual Report 2021-22 (MSME, Annual Report, 2021-2022)

Total number of 3190 PMEGP Projects was sanctioned by involving Margin Money Subsidy of Rs. 73.13 Crore in NE States during the year 2021-22. Performance of the PMEGP in NE States in 2021-22 (31.12.2021). The north eastern states received a total of 37597.28, with the margin money amounting to 7313.25. 3190 units were assisted, with an estimated employment of 25520.

Table 7: State-wise Micro Enterprises (projects) assisted under PMEGP in North- East (for setting up of new PMEGP units & 2nd dose for existing units)

S.No	State	2017-18	2018-19	2019-20	2020-21	2021-22 (upto 31.12.2021)
1	Arunachal Pradesh	209	280	211	98	86
2	Assam	2282	3737	2587	2939	1282
3	Manipur	600	1291	1173	1556	460
4	Meghalaya	75	390	377	359	206
5	Mizoram	249	1123	760	810	189
6	Nagaland	930	1208	1109	740	490
7	Sikkim	37	55	79	842	24
8	Tripura	1116	1179	963	57	453
Total		5498	9263	7259	7401	3190

Source: Annual Report 2021-22 (MSME, Annual Report, 2021-2022)

The total number of Micro Enterprises (projects) assisted under PMEGP in the North-East (for the establishment of new PMEGP units and the second dose for existing units) was 9263 in 2018-19.

Distribution and Growth of MSMEs among the North East India:

Distribution of Proprietary MSMEs by Gender of Owners is an important role of the MSMEs sector in the North Eastern Region (NSS 73rd Round).

Table 8: State-wise Distribution of Proprietary MSMEs by Gender of Owners (NSS 73rd Round)

S.No	State	Male	Female	All	Share of State among All MSMEs with Male Owners (Per cent)	Share of State among All MSMEs with Female Owners (Per cent)
1	Arunachal Pradesh	16153	6274	22427	1.02	2.35
2	Assam	1128411	66665	1195076	70.99	25.02
3	Manipur	86383	86604	172987	5.43	32.48
4	Meghalaya	72191	39462	111653	4.54	14.79
5	Mizoram	20439	13698	34137	1.28	5.13
6	Nagaland	65778	20865	86643	4.14	7.82
7	Sikkim	20880	5036	25916	1.31	1.89
8	Tripura	179169	28042	207211	11.29	10.52
All		1589404	266646	1856050	100	100

Source: Annual Report 2021-22 (MSME, Annual Report, 2021-2022)

The NSS 73rd round distributed proprietary MSMEs by gender of owners by state. A total of 1589404 males and 266646 females were assigned, for a total of 1856050. The share of states among all MSMEs with male and female owners was 100%.

Conclusion:

According to the analysis, the Micro, Small, and Medium Enterprise (MSME) sector has emerged as a very important segment that contributes significantly to job creation, innovation, exports, and inclusive economic growth. The reason for this is that the MSME sector has the ability to produce cost-effective products, and the government is providing full support to this sector. They offer one of the highest per capita employment investment opportunities, reducing rural-to-urban migration and providing local employment opportunities. The United Nations Development Programme recognizes the MSME sector's contribution to sustainable development in achieving the SDGs in developing countries. Aside from the potential to employ millions, MSMEs play an important role in preserving and promoting the use of low-cost indigenous solutions and products. MSMEs play an important role in the development of North Eastern states in India; despite accounting for only 1.5 percent of India's MSMEs, they contribute nearly 62 percent to the economy in terms of employment, output, and exports.

This is especially true in the North East Region (NER), where the sector accounts for approximately 62 percent of industrial output. The North East Region (NER), which currently accounts for only 1.5 percent of MSMEs in India, is a rich melting pot of cultures, distinct tribes, and a plethora of distinct crafts - it has enormous potential to become the country's hub of Micro, Small, and Medium Enterprises. However, while India's trade with neighboring countries such as Nepal, Bhutan, Bangladesh, Cambodia, Lao PDR, Myanmar, Thailand, and Vietnam has grown at a CAGR of 23%, the NER's share in this trade has remained static, hovering consistently in the range of 1-2% and accounting for only 5% of total exports from India to Bangladesh, Myanmar, and Bhutan. As a result, MSMEs have created more GDPs and created more job

opportunities, which has a positive impact on the North East Indian economy through economic development.

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